

Appendix VI
ACH diagnosticity matrix

Beliefs G1:G2	G1: Send messages to all pages' followers	G2: Delete advertising messages
People get frustrated when they receive messages from 3rd parties	I	C
Some people may need information about products from 3rd parties and are willing to receive them	C	I
If the company page gets hacked, then spam messages can be sent out to followers, which eventually will ruin the company's branding	I	N
Inconsistency Score:	-2	-1
Beliefs G3:G4	G3: Track people's data	G4: Prevent all kinds of fraud and Be in charge of all the chatbots, or other automatic functions within the messenger
Tracking people's data allows hackers to get information about a specific person and use it in a bad way.	I	C
Tracking data can help crime activity get solved.	C	N
When the government is in charge of some functions within Messenger, it is less likely for hackers to get information about a specific person.	N	C
Inconsistency Score:	-1	0
Beliefs G5:G6	G5: Create individual ads	G6: Use the same ads for all users
Individual ads catch people's attention since they are evenly tailored for specific types of users	C	I
Creating different types of ads takes much more time, and sometimes results can not be successful	I	C
Having a lot of features to create ads within an app brings more frustration to the advertiser since they might get lost in settings	N	N
Individual ads help better track users' behavior and see whether they work or need to be changed	C	I
Inconsistency Score:	-1	-2
Beliefs G7:G8	G7: Target non-brand-aware users	G8: Restrict advertisers from doing extensive targeting

Targeting non-brand aware users can increase company's reach and visibility	C	I
Targeting non-brand aware users may lead to their frustration if they are not interested in the company's services	I	C
Some advertisers may use targeting methods as sending out spam messages and advertising inappropriate products	I	C
Advertisers use Messenger in order to reach out to more people, otherwise they will not use it	C	N
Inconsistency Score:	-2	-1
Beliefs G9:G10	G9: Host webinars/online events	G10: Want the app to be as basic as possible
Webinars/online events may help to increase the company's visibility	C	N
Various topics are discussed at webinars that can teach many things to users. So the pastime will become more interesting and useful for users.	C	N
Facebook already makes it possible to launch webinars on the site, and there is no need to do this in the messenger.	I	C
Webinars on Messenger will help to attract new clients for the company easier and faster.	C	N
Inconsistency Score:	-1	0
Beliefs G14:G15	G14: Impact people's choices	G15: Impact people's choices
People prefer freedom, so if they notice that government tries to rule over their lives, they will delete Messenger	N	I
Government tries to prevent users from malicious attacks by third parties by impacting users' choices	N	C
Inconsistency Score:	0	-1
Beliefs G16:G17	G16: Create a "circle" of customers to chat with	G17: Move messages from 3rd parties to spam folder
Messages from unknown 3rd parties frustrate users	I	C
Users can get in touch with companies by themselves if they need any information, no need to chat with them	I	N
Messenger already has a feature of moving messages from 3rd parties to the "other messages" folder, so there is a high		

likelihood that a very small amount of users will receive messages	N	N
Inconsistency Score:	-2	0
Beliefs G21:G22	G21: Edit stories	G22: See all messages/stories and etc. which have been edited
People are willing to post more stories if they can later edit them, so there will be no need to delete and upload new version again	C	N
In order to be able to track users' actions, it is better to see all their edited stories/messages before they were edited.	N	C
When users edit stories, they do not want others to see the previous ones. Users prefer privacy over anything else.	C	I
Inconsistency Score:	0	-1
Beliefs G26:G27	G26: Restrict some people from seeing any information related to me	G27: Get all the detailed information about the person
Seeing all the detailed information about the user is necessary if crime activity happens, it will help to solve such cases much faster	I	C
Users may churn from the platform if the platform does not support their privacy	C	N
Another chat service, Telegram, refused to share data with the government and the number of users of the system increased many times over.	C	N
Inconsistency Score:	-1	0
Beliefs G28:G29	G28: Delete others' messages	G29: Constrain others from deleting my messages
Deleting others' messages may lead to users' frustration and churn since they lose their rights to speak	I	C
People may misuse such function	I	C
Inconsistency Score:	-2	0

Beliefs G11:G12:G13	G11: Avoid ad blockers	G12: Block ads while playing games	G13: Filter ads
Users get frustrated when they receive ads while playing games	I	C	N
Ads help educate the	C	I	N

consumers			
With the help of advertisements, a consumer gets the best possible options	C	I	C
Inconsistency Score:	-1	-2	0
Beliefs G18:G19:G20	G18: Have secret chats	G19: Listen to all voice messages	G20: Read all the messages from all chats
Users want to keep messages safe from the hacker attacks	C	I	I
Secret chatting function does not support cloud backup functionality	N	I	I
Messages in secret chats can't be forwarded.	C	I	I
Inconsistency Score:	0	-3	-3
Beliefs G23:G24:G25	G23: Play all kinds of games and Integrate all browser games	G24: Remove gaming feature	G25: Restrict some games
More games may drive more users to the platform	C	I	I
Gaming addiction negatively affects eyesight and also results in Insomnia, so people may start avoiding it	I	C	C
If some users do not want to play games, they may avoid it. However, it does not mean that such a feature should be fully removed from Messenger.	C	I	I
Inconsistency Score:	-1	-2	-2